

Surgical Removal of Lingually Placed Supernumerary Tooth : Case Report

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Abstract

Teeth that erupt in addition to the normal number of teeth are known as supernumerary teeth. Supernumerary teeth are the most prevalent type of dental abnormality. The maxillary anterior area is where extra teeth are typically found. They can appear in any arch at any position and can be single or numerous, unilateral or bilateral. These teeth may be found in either the permanent or primary dentition. Many clinical issues could arise from their existence. As a result, they require the proper diagnosis and care. A comprehensive clinical examination and radiographic examination are used to diagnose extra teeth. This paper includes a case study of a patient with unilateral impacted supernumerary teeth along with a synopsis of the causes and treatments of these teeth.

Keywords – Supernumerary tooth, surgical extraction, lingual flap

Introduction

A supernumerary tooth is one that is not part of the usual set of teeth.¹ With a frequency of more than 3%, reports of these teeth are more prevalent among the mongoloid racial group.^{2,3} In comparison to primary dentition, the prevalence of extra teeth is higher in permanent dentition. Supernumerary teeth are found in 1–3% of permanent dentition and 0.3–0.6% of primary dentition, according to Koch et al.⁴ According to Rajab and Hamden,⁵ the prevalence of these teeth is 0.3–0.8% in the primary dentition and 0.1–3.8% in the permanent dentition. Because of the voids in the primary dentition that permit the emergence of these teeth in a normal alignment, supernumerary teeth may go unnoticed at this stage of development.⁶ The morphology and position of extraneous teeth determine their classification.

In primary dentition, supernumerary teeth often have normal or conical morphologies. The morphology of these teeth varies in the permanent dentition.

Conical teeth, tuberculate supernumerary teeth (barrel-shaped teeth with multiple tubercles in the crown and incomplete or absent root), supplemental teeth (supernumerary teeth with shape resembling normal teeth), and odontome (multiple small tooth like structures or a single irregular mass) are some examples of these variations. Supernumerary teeth are classified as mesiodens, which are extra teeth between the maxillary central incisors; paramolars, which are extra teeth next to molars; distomolars, which are extra teeth farthest from the last molar; and parapremolars, which are extra teeth in the premolar region. One or two supernumerary teeth found commonly in anterior maxilla followed by mandibular premolar area. Multiple supernumerary teeth seen commonly in premolar area.^{7,8}

Many theories have been proposed

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to explain aetiology of supernumerary teeth. These include atavism, dichotomy of tooth bud, and localized hyperactivity of dental lamina resulting in formation of additional tooth germ, genetic factors and syndromes.

Atavism: The re-emergence of an ancestral condition is known as atavism, which is a form of long-distance heredity or phylogenetic reversion. There have been suggestions that it is a throwback to evolution. Man's teeth have become smaller and fewer in number as a result of phylogenetic evolution, and extra premolars could be an atavistic feature of the premolar region. According to this theory, human dentition may have reverted to that of an ancestor who had more teeth.^{9,10}

Dichotomy: Dichotomy is division of tooth bud into two teeth of equal size or one normal and one dysmorphic tooth with two equal or different sized parts. Division in the developing tooth bud can give rise to supernumerary tooth and a normal tooth.¹¹

Hyperactivity of dental lamina: Because of their size, the epithelial remains can stimulate and regulate the growth of the dental papilla. An additional tooth bud forms and additional odontogenic structure develops if the epithelial remnants are exposed to induction stimuli.¹⁰ The most widely recognised explanation for the production of supernumerary teeth is the localised and autonomous hyperactivity of the dental lamina.¹² A eumorphic tooth develops from the lingual extension of an extra tooth bud, whereas a primitive tooth is created by the proliferation of dental lamina epithelial remains.¹³

Genetics: The growth of extra teeth is also influenced by environmental and genetic factors. Recurrence of extra teeth in monozygotic twins and members of the same family also showed a hereditary component. 14 Siblings, twins, and other family members have been documented to have extra teeth in a number of case reports.¹⁵

Associated syndromes: Various hereditary syndromes found to be associated with hyperdontia. These syndromes are Crouzon syndrome, Cleidocranial dysplasia, Ehlers-Danlos syndrome, Gardner's syndrome,¹⁶ Goldenhar syndrome¹⁷, Hallermann-Streiff syndrome,¹⁸ Orofaciodigital syndrome type I¹⁹, Incontinentia pigmenti,²⁰ Marfan syndrome, Nance-Horan syndrome, and cleft lip and palate.²¹

Case report

A patient aged 21 years came to the department of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopaedics at Babu Banarasi Das College of Dental Sciences with chief complaint of forwardly placed upper front teeth. Intraoral examination showed permanent teeth till third molar present in each quadrant of mandibular arch and in

maxillary arch all permanent teeth erupted. Patient had class II molar relation with increased overjet and crowding in maxillary and Mandibular anterior region. It was observed that mandibular right second molar is grossly carious and the left maxillary 3rd molar is absent. Lateral cephalogram and orthopantomogram were taken for orthodontic analysis and treatment planning.

On analyzing orthopantomogram, it was observed that one teeth is impacted in right canine-premolar region in mandibular arch.(fig.1) Crown shape of tooth was similar to premolar and roots are shorter than normal. Surgical extraction was planned as a treatment for this case for which the patient was referred to department of oral & maxillofacial surgery.

Intra oral periapical radiographs (IOPA) were taken with SLOB technique to see exact position of the tooth whether it is located buccally or lingually. It was confirmed from these radiographs that the tooth is located on lingual side. Extra-oral examination presented convex facial profile with incompetent lips. Patient had no medical history regarding any type of diseases or medication.

Routine blood investigation was done for complete blood count, bleeding time, clotting time, random blood sugar the values for which were under normal limits. Viral markers like HIV, HbsAg and HCV was done and was non reactive. The surgical removal of the supernumerary tooth was done by giving a crevicular incision on lingual side from right molar to left premolars without giving releasing incision. Lingual flap was reflected and the location of the supernumerary tooth on the lingual cortex was exposed.(fig 2) Straight surgical hand piece was used with round bur and 701 straight bur to remove the bone on the bulge of lingual cortex to expose the supernumerary tooth in a controlled manner in order to prevent injury to inferior alveolar nerve. Extraction of supernumerary tooth was done in toto (fig 3& 4) followed by extraction of 44 and 14. The extraction socket of the supernumerary teeth was placed with PRF which was prepared by drawing 10 ml blood from the patient in a sterilized syringe and transferred to test tube to make platelet rich fibrin in a centrifuge machine at 3000 rpm (800g) for 10 minutes. PRF was made and placed in the extraction socket of supernumerary tooth to enhanced healing. Closure was done using 3-0 mersilk and sling suture technique pressure pack was given and antibiotics and analgesics was prescribed for 5 days along with post extraction instructions.

Discussion

In permanent dentition, supernumerary teeth are most prevalent. Extra teeth may occasionally remain

Fig 1. Orthopantomogram

Fig 2. Reflection of lingual flap

Fig 3. Exposure of supernumerary tooth

Fig 4. Extracted supernumerary tooth

impacted or may occasionally emerge in the oral cavity. A tooth that remains in position and does not erupt is called an impacted tooth. In permanent dentition, eruption failure is a common dental abnormality. Teeth impaction can lead to a number of issues, including altered tooth mobility, functional ramifications, and aesthetic issues. The complex, genetically based process of permanent tooth emergence involves the eruptive movement

of dental germs along predefined pathways to reach the occlusal level at a given time. The intricacy of the eruption process can lead to several difficulties, including delayed and unsuccessful eruption of teeth.²²

The aetiology of tooth impaction involves both systemic and local causes. crowding, ectopically positioned tooth germs, supernumerary teeth, dense mucosa or overlying bone, and the early loss or protracted retention

of deciduous teeth are examples of local variables. Impaction can be caused by systemic causes like as rickets, congenital syphilis, progeria, achondroplasia, and endocrine disorders.²³

Supernumerary teeth were shown to be prevalent in primary dentitions (0.8%), whereas in permanent dentitions (2.1%), according to Brook.²⁴ They could be in one or both jaws, single or many, unilateral or bilateral, erupted or impacted. Multiple extra teeth are uncommon in persons without any additional comorbidities or disorders.²⁵ There is a correlation between some illnesses such as cleidocranial dysplasia, Gardner syndrome, and cleft lip and palate and the higher frequency of extra teeth. In patients with unilateral cleft lip or palate, or both, the incidence of extra permanent teeth in the cleft region was observed to be 22.2%.²⁶ In individuals with cleidocranial dysplasia, the incidence of extra teeth varied from 22% in the maxillary incisor region to 5% in the molar region.²⁷ Males are affected about twice as much as females in the permanent dentition, while there is no discernible difference in primary supernumerary teeth between the sexes.²⁸

As in this case study, extra teeth might occasionally remain impacted. For effective orthodontic treatment planning, such teeth must undergo a thorough radiographic evaluation. Diagnostic tools like tube shift radiography and cone beam computed tomography can be used to pinpoint the precise location of an impacted supernumerary tooth and how it relates to adjacent hard and soft tissue components. In order to attain the right occlusion and aesthetics, treatment options may include orthodontic alignment and the extraction of excess teeth.²⁹

Extraction of supernumerary teeth is advised in conditions such as: Delayed eruption of adjacent tooth, altered eruption and displacement of adjacent tooth, any pathology associated to supernumerary tooth, for orthodontic treatment, when such tooth is present in bony area designated for implant insertion, or when bone grafting in cleft patients is compromised due to presence of supernumerary tooth.³⁰

Indications for monitoring of supernumerary teeth without extraction includes satisfactory eruption of adjacent tooth, no orthodontic treatment is needed for patient and no pathology linked to supernumerary tooth.³⁰

The presence of impacted, unnoticed supernumerary tooth may interfere with orthodontic alignment and space closure. Extraction of such teeth is advised for orthodontic treatment. In present case report the impacted supernumerary tooth present close to roots of permanent canine and premolars in right mandibular arch. Extraction of these was planned for orthodontic treatment pro-

gress.

Conclusion

Supernumerary teeth are extra teeth beyond the normal complement that are present in both dentitions. Men are particularly affected by these teeth, which are common in permanent dentition. Supernumerary teeth can arise unilaterally or bilaterally, in one or both dental arches, in one or more teeth, erupted or impacted. Mesiodens are the most prevalent type of extra teeth, and then extra premolars. It is essential to properly diagnose and treat these teeth in order to minimise any potential issues that may arise from having too many teeth. These complications include crowding, displacement, dilations, and cyst formation, among others, and they may interfere with orthodontic tooth movement. If the extra tooth is asymptomatic, there is no need to treat it; however, routine clinical and radiological surveillance is necessary to guard against any unfavourable consequences it may cause.

References

1. Garvey MT, Barry HJ, Blake M. Supernumerary teeth-an overview of classification, diagnosis, and management. *J Can Dent Assoc* 1999; 65:612-6.
2. Niswander JD, Sujaku C. Congenital anomalies of teeth in the Japanese children. *Am J PhysAnthropol* 1963;21:569-74
3. Davis PJ. Hypodontia and hyperdontia of permanent teeth in Hong Kong school children. *Community Dent Oral Epidemiol* 1987;15:218-20.
4. Koch H, Schwartz O, Klausen B. Indications for surgical removal of supernumerary teeth in the premaxilla. *Int J Oral MaxillofacSurg* 1986; 15:273-81.
5. Rajab LD, Hamdan MA. Supernumerary teeth: Review of the literature and a survey of 152 cases. *Int J Paediatr Dent* 2002; 12:244-54.
6. Scheiner MA, Sampson WJ. Supernumerary teeth: A review of the literature and four case reports. *Aust Dent J* 1997;42:160-5.
7. So L.L.Y. Unusual supernumerary teeth. *Angle Orthod* 1990;60:289- 92.
8. Kolokitha G O-E ,Papadopoulou A K. Impaction and apical root angulation of the maxillary central incisor due to supernumerary teeth: Combined surgical and orthodontic treatment. *Am J Orthod Dentofacial Orthop* 2008;134:153-60.
9. J. D. Smith, "Hyperdontia: report of case," *Journal of the American Dental Association*, vol. 79, no. 5, pp. 1191-1192, 1969.
10. R. P. Anthonappa, N. M. King, and A. B. Rabie, "Aetiology of supernumerary teeth: a literature review," *European Archives of Paediatric Dentistry*, vol. 14, pp. 279-288, 2013.
11. W. Bateson, "On numerical variation in teeth, with a discussion of conception of homology," *Proceedings of Zoological Society of London*, vol. 102, p. 115, 1982.
12. G. V. Black, "Supernumerary teeth," *Dental Summary*, vol. 29, pp. 83-110, 1909.
13. S. N. Sykaras, "Mesiodens in primary and permanent dentitions: report of a case," *Oral Surgery, Oral Medicine, Oral Pathology*, vol. 39, no. 6, pp. 870-874, 1975.
14. Santos APP, Ammari MM, Moliterno LFM, Junior JC. First report of bilateral supernumerary teeth associated with both primary and permanent maxillary canines. *Journal of Oral Science* 2009;51(1):145-150.
15. Mallineni SK. Supernumerary teeth: Review of literature with recent updates. *Conference Papers in Science*. 2014;1-7.
16. J. Groden, A. Thliveris, W. Samowitz et al., "Identification and characterization of the familial adenomatous polyposis coli gene," *Cell*, vol. 66, pp. 589-600, 1991.
17. K. Bogusiak, P. Arkuszewski, K. Skorek-Stachnik, and M. Kozakiewicz,

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- "Treatment strategy in Goldenhar syndrome," *Journal of Craniofacial Surgery*, vol. 25, pp. 177–183, 2014.
18. P. Robotta and E. Schafer, "Hallermand-Streiff syndrome: case report and literature review," *Quintessence International*, vol. 42, no. 4, pp. 331–338, 2011.
 19. M. I. Ferrante, G. Giorgio, S. A. Feather et al., "Identification of the gene for oral-facial-digital type 1 syndrome," *The American Journal of Human Genetics*, vol. 68, no. 3, pp. 569–576, 2001.
 20. D. A. Himelhoch, B. J. Scott, and R. A. Olsen, "Dental defects in incontinentiapigmenti: case report," *Pediatric Dentistry*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 236–239, 1987.
 21. Neville BW, Damm DD, Allen CM, Bouquot JE. *Oral and maxillofacial pathology*. 2002; 2nd ed WB Saunders, Philadelphia: 69-73.
 22. Patil S, Maheshwari S. Prevalence of impacted and supernumerary teeth in North Indian population. *J ClinExp Dent*.2014;6(2):e116-e120.
 23. Kaur S et al. Rare occurrence of impacted and inverted maxillary third molar - A case report. *Int. J. Curr. Res. Med. Sci*.2018; 4(4): 53-55.
 24. Brook AH. Dental anomalies of number, form and size: their prevalence in British schoolchildren. *J IntAssoc Dent Child* 1974; 5:37-53.
 25. Scheiner MA, Sampson WJ. Supernumerary teeth: a review of the literature and four case reports. *Aust Dent J* 1997; 42:160-5.
 26. Vichi M, Franchi L. Abnormalities of the maxillary incisors in children with cleft lip and palate. *ADSC J Dent Child* 1995; 62:412-7.
 27. Jensen BL, Kreiborg S. Development of the dentition in cleidocranial dysplasia. *J Oral Pathol Med* 1990; 19:89-93.
 28. Kinirons MJ. Uneruptedpremaxillary supernumerary teeth. A study of their occurrence in males and females. *Br Dent J* 1982; 153:110.
 29. Rahman MA, Alam MM, Hossai MZ. Orthodontic management of supernumerary teeth- a case report. *Ban J Orthod and Dentofac Orthop*, Oct 2011; Vol-2, No. 1, p 30-33.
 30. Therese GM, Dent BSc, Barry HJ, Blake M, Dent BSc. Supernumerary teeth- An overview of classification, diagnosis and management *Can Dent Assoc*.1999;65;612-6